

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS FOR PREPARING ADOLESCENTS FOR FAMILY LIFE

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Abstract. *This article is one of the most essential issues and it is related to the pedagogical and psychological preparation of teenagers for the family issues and the corporation between the society and families in establishing family education.*

Keywords: *teenager, family, marriage, spirituality, perfection, family Psychology, psychological preparation for a family, psychological maturity, maturity as an individual, motherhood and childhood.*

The relevance of the article: the basis of our society is to further strengthen and develop the institution of the family, to protect the legal and socio – economic interests of families, especially young families, as well as to qualitatively take all the work carried out to a new level to strengthen support, to raise the role of the family in the upbringing of a In the psychological category literature, definitions of the concept of family are given as follows. In this regard, our countryman Sh.M.Paying tribute to Mirziyoev's words, " in the process of forming strong families, socially reserving motherhood and childhood, creating favorable conditions for the birth of children who are physically healthy in families, strong energy, effectively creating strong cooperation between families and the public in the process of organizing family education, attention is paid at the level of state policy. In particular, we can see that the relevance of preparing young people for family life and introducing modern exemplary family criteria into marriage, defects that appeared in adolescence, subsequently, preserved for life, can negatively affect the spirituality of both society and family. Therefore, it is insisted that pedagogical-psychological training of adolescents in family life is considered an urgent problem. Indeed, the family is a sacred Dargah, because it is a dwelling made up of the closest relatives of a person, each member of which supports each other, has a sincere relationship with each other, helps each other, helps to realize and support their mistakes, and in this environment a person matures. Abu Rayhon Beruniy Kham, one of our qomusi scholars on the problems of preparing adolescents for family life, praises that there must be" the core of tidiness and orastal nobility; alloma talks about the connection between a person's external pleasant appearance and his moral image in order for a couple to have a healthy relationship in the family, arguing that "washing the tooth, keeping the eyes and eyelids clean, putting a push on them, and dyeing the hair as needed, taking and grinding nails" is the basis of human health and mental purity. These thoughts have not lost their relevance even in modern times, because the fact that family members, spouses follow these guidelines is one of the grounds for family harmony. The idea that a person with morality should first of all be an example in his own behavior, in the culture of treatment, in living life, in family stability is an example of the scientist's instructive views on family ethics: "a person is domineering in his passions, able to change them, educate his soul, transform negative aspects into praises, treat him with spiritual medicine, and gradually,

The issue of family and family relations is expressed in its own way in the work "event address". While illuminating various aspects of family relations, Ibn Sina first makes a series of

demands to the head of the family of the womb. The head of the family, he writes, should perfectly master the issues of upbringing in the family, both theoretically and practically. If the head of the family is inexperienced, he will not be able to raise his members well, in the end he will not achieve good positive results, poor upbringing can badly affect not only this family, but also neighbors, neighborhoods. Raising a child in a family is their primary function, regardless of the position of the parents in society, according to Ibn Sina. In these thoughts, Izox emphasized the role of the Social Institute of the family, which is considered an important focus of all educational influence, in educating the younger generation as a perfect person, and that young people who are stepping into family life should be psychologically, pedagogically, in terms of readiness for the family, and we can see that these thoughts are The establishment of a Family Life Circle is the reason for the content of positive interpersonal relationships not only between family members, but also between members of society.

The robustness of families is a decisive factor determining the economic, social, political, national security of society, its prosperity, development. The issue of preparing young people for family life, which is the main way to ensure the strength of families and correctly solve this issue at the same time, which is currently increasing the threat of economic, social, political, environmental, internal and external factors that pose a serious threat to our society, for the development of mankind, for the prospects of our independence, is

Family problems, the problem of preparing family and students for family life have always been the focus of researchers. From the psychologists of Uzbekistan G.B.Shoumarov, V.M.Karimova, E.Goziev, B.Kadyrov, H.Rahimov, N.A.Soginov, O.Musurmonova, I.X.We can study the research work of Karimova, and others devoted to theoretical-practical issues of preparing adolescents for family life. In particular, family education in relation to the features of interaction in families, problems of family and spiritual and moral education. Musurmonova, on the issues of spiritual and moral education of children in the family. Inomova conducted scientific research.

A family is a small group based on marriage or childbirth. Its members are intertwined with the unity, mutual assistance and spiritual responsibility of the monk. The most important social tasks of the family are to continue the human race, raise children, effectively organize the living conditions and free time of family members.

Adolescence is a period that changes a person from childhood to youth and, in turn, differs from other periods in its relatively sharper, more complex course. The fact that adolescence is a difficult, complex period is associated with many psychological, physiological, social factors. During this period, all aspects of development: physical, mental, moral, social and the essence of the content of the like also change. During this period, serious changes occur in the life of a teenager, in his psyche, in the physiological states of his organism, in his social state. In most cases, different traditions are observed in them, which are opposite to each other. By this period, the idea that the child is no longer a "child" and at the same time is not yet a "big" L.S.Vigotsky advanced. In his time, G.B.Shoumarov approaches the problems in this regard in detail, and his attitude towards himself and those around him acquires a completely different character. The system of his interests, social orientation is formed again, self-awareness, assessment, values change. He increases the importance of his "I" and the same "I" for nothing, opined. Therefore, it is necessary to organize an educational process taking into account the changes in the characteristic character traits of the adolescent age. In order to mature as an independent person, on the basis of

family and school cooperation, they will have to prepare for an independent family life as a result of the formation of moral, educational knowledge, skills in them. It is advisable for parents to focus more on adolescent upbringing than ever during this period to carry educational influences while realizing the changes in it.

That is why the family is considered the most important branch of society, and the state is constantly paying great attention to educate healthy young generations on all sides is the most basic social task. The implementation of this directly in the Family, Educational Institutions has a positive effect. Of course, the role of the family is great in the formation of our children as well-educated, mannered, common sense, affectionate and patriotic. One of the most effective means of moral education in the family is communication. Because interpersonal relationships in a family, sibling statuses between family members, lead to productive parent-child relationships.

We drew our attention to the following in increasing the effectiveness of preparing adolescents for family life by creating a targeted educational and educational system in the cooperation of family and neighborhood institutions on the basis of a pedagogical-psychological approach to family life in secondary schools.

We have set a number of tasks in this regard:

- formation of adolescents' knowledge on the basis of our national values of readiness for family life;

- a systematic approach to the education of teenage students through Family, School and Neighborhood Cooperation;

- Organization of the educational process through thoughts that are presented to teenage students in the works of Oriental allomas;

- study of the role and importance of the family in the upbringing of the younger generation, the impact of family relations on the formation of harmonious younger generations;

From the above points, it can be seen that family relations are determined by the existing social, economic, ideological relations in society, as a relatively independent phenomenon, and change under their influence. Accordingly, each society establishes its own relationship based on a suitable family type that changes.

The most important thing in the life of every person is family. "The family is sacred to me. The holiness is that no matter who works first, there will never be a result if the family does not pay special attention to upbringing, atmosphere in the family, honesty in the family, attitude, upbringing. Therefore, I pay a lot of attention to the upbringing of my children. I have a special attitude both to each child and to my granddaughter. I know the special character of each granddaughter, I know her dream, desire... how much do you have the right to say that a person is happy? If you are happy with your family, you have the right to say that you are happy. Not just my family, I find myself happy when my people are happy." is. Based on the thoughts of our countryman, we lose our identity if we do not save the family". "Today The Times are changing rapidly. Who makes these changes feel more than everyone else – young people. May young people be in harmony with the demands of the present era. But at the same time, do not forget about oneself. ... What do we achieve this at the expense of? At the expense of upbringing, upbringing and only upbringing". Consequently, the scientific approach to the issues of family education is one of the important directions of the strategy of actions that determined the development of our country, and the definition of its conditions is among the important tasks. Indeed, neighborhoods, districts, cities and regions, countries are also made up of families.

Therefore, the important role of the family in society, spiritual moral, educational significance, dignity and the implementation of these socio-pedagogical tasks is an urgent issue today. Because the family is the basis of society and has many centuries of strong spiritual foundations. Despite the fact that much attention is paid to the issue of strengthening the family, the violent changes in today's world are causing new problems in this matter. One of the situations of particular concern is the growing number of cases of divorce as a result of the preparation of teenage youth for the family, various attitudes towards family and mutual misunderstandings without the lack of knowledge about the family. For this reason, in secondary schools, it is one of the urgent problems for young students to know family psychological relationships, to mean the holiness of the family, to formulate family management skills, knowledge about the upbringing of children. The reason is that nowadays students who have graduated from secondary schools do not have enough skills about family relationships, adapt to the environment in their family and cannot fully realize their future either. In the process of studying the pedagogical and psychological factors of preparing adolescents for family life, the following factors can be attributed to:

- formation of knowledge of interpersonal relationships, Family, Educational phenomena in adolescents;
- the use of universal values in the formation of issues of moral education in adolescents;
- secondary schools, family neighborhood cooperation;
- by organizing activities on spiritual and moral education for students of teenage age;
- improving the work of preparing students of adolescent age for their independent life by directing them to the profession;
- further improvement of this process by attracting specialists in family education;

Family-as a small community formed on the basis of Social, natural factors, it is to create conditions for the relationship between individuals of both sexes to build a life-building offspring together, not only to give birth to a child, but to make an independent step into life by maturing them spiritually and physically. Therefore, in order for such a huge responsibility to be successfully fulfilled, it is of particular importance for a teenager to be ready for family relations from an early age, to be psychologically prepared for the family in a prosperous life.

Therefore, by organizing activities on spiritual and moral education for the younger generation, it is possible to develop in them the attitude towards the family, moral, moral qualities, loyalty to the motherland.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth saying that today in our country there is a lot of attention paid to young people, their acquisition of knowledge and occupation. It is only in a family where a healthy psychological environment is decided that it is possible to bring up the future generation, which will be harmonious and suitable for the country Cory. From this point of view, it will be appropriate to organize short-term training courses on the preparation of future brides and grooms for Family Associations and prepare young people for the family socially, pedagogically-psychologically by attaching to them specialists in Family Psychology, fathers and mothers with life experience in the family. Through this, we have made a significant contribution to the formation of individuals who serve the well-being of the people to the prosperity of a harmonious, healthy and independent-minded country in society.

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